

Arbiter of Morality: Hercule Poirot as Judge and Philosopher in Agatha Christie's *Murder on the Orient Express*

Annie Tehillah A,

Research Scholar,

Department of English and Foreign Languages,

Mother Teresa Women's University,

Kodaikanal.

Research Supervisor

Dr. A. Muthu Meena Losini,

Assistant Professor,

Department of English and Foreign Languages,

Mother Teresa Women's University,

Kodaikanal.

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Abstract

Agatha Christie's *Murder on the Orient Express* is one of the main novels that explore the Humane Nature where it shows that Morality won't abide by the Law all the times. In this paper, it particularly analyses how Hercule Poirot acts as a Arbiter of Morality, where he understands the sense of morality without the lens of Law. Christie portrayed the raw emotion of how a hurt heart and mind leads someone to go into their ways though it's a crime. This paper examines Poirot's decision making process and his philosophical views of right and wrong.

Key Words: Arbiter, Dilemma, Justice, Morality, Right and Wrong.

Agatha Christie's *Murder on the Orient Express* (1934) is one of her most celebrated novels, and it plays a crucial role in the genre of Detective fiction. Unlike other works, this novel in particular stirs the human emotions where a murder of the murderer is portrayed as Justice.

The novel is set on the most luxurious train of the time known as ‘the Orient Express’ which starts from Istanbul and gets stuck due to the heavy snowstorm when it passes through Belgrade and Vinkovci. During that time, a murder takes place, a man named Ratchett was murdered. So, Poirot steps in to find the killer.

Poirot was accompanied by his friend and fellow Belgian, M. Bouc, and Dr. Constantine. The three of them examined the body, and that the victim was stabbed 12 to 15 times, some of the stabbings were deep and some were caused by both the right and left hand, above all, he was stabbed, even after he dies. They also found that the window was open, assumed that the murderer might have escaped from there, but the snow makes it not possible. Poirot also found a woman’s handkerchief with a letter ‘H’ on it, and a pipe cleaner was also found. Most importantly, they found a loaded gun under the pillow. A stop watch was also found but it stopped at 12:45, which they assumed that the time of his death. Based on the evidence, it is clear that one of the passengers is the killer.

“ ‘At half an hour after midnight we ran into the snowdrift. No one can have left the train since then’. M. Bouc said solemnly. ‘The murderer is with us-on the train now...’ ”(*Murder on the Orient Express*,49)

After the thorough investigation of the victim’s room, they have found a piece of burnt paper. Poirot stated that the paper was burned by the victim itself not the killer, so he held it over the flame of the spirit lamp, and words forms themselves slowly. It showed ‘---- member little Daisy Armstrong’ (*Murder on the Orient Express*, 69). With that, Poirot revealed the victim’s true identity that his real name is Casseti. He is the murderer of Daisy Armstrong.

The Armstrong case sent shockwaves all over the America. Casseti kidnapped little Daisy asked for the ransom from her family, her father, Colonel Armstrong who though paid the ransom. She was found dead. Mrs Armstrong was expecting another child during that time, the shock discovery of her daughter’s death made her to give birth prematurely and that killed herself and the baby. This tragic incident made the broke hearted Colonel to shot himself. Following this disaster, another tragic too happened which was the death of the nursemaid. She was falsely accused by the police, so she committed suicide by throwing herself from a window. (*Murder on the Orient Express*, 72)

About six months after, Cassetti was arrested but he was released by double crossing his own gang. After the release, he fled from America and changed his name to Ratchett. He's been living as a gentleman of leisure. The burnt paper clearly revealed that one of acquaintances to the Armstrong family must have committed the murder. So, Poirot began interrogating everyone in the train.

The Orient Express was fully booked in the dry season, which seemed strange. Poirot interrogated every passenger in the train. The Passengers were all from different classes and races, more or less it seemed one third of the whole Earth's population was present on the train. The passengers were,

- Mrs. Hubbard, who seemed as the cheery spirit among them and she flaunts her luxury and how she gained from her many husbands.
- Colonel Arbuthnot, who is the British Army officer, and was seen with Mary Debenham. He always maintains a low profile and he also happens to be the one who smokes pipe which aligns with the pipe cleaner, which was found in the victim's room.
- Princess Dragomiroff, a Russian Noblewoman who maintains high profile.
- She was accompanied by Hildegarde Schmit, a maid, who claimed that she saw another conductor in the late midnight, who was small in person and had a feminine voice, and also where the train conductor's uniform without button was found in her room.
- Count Andrenyi, he is a Hungarian Diplomat who is married to Countess Andrenyi. Both of them rarely left their room.
- Mary Debenham, an English governess, who was seen with Colonel Arbuthnot.
- Hector MacQueen, Ratchett's Secretary, who was often mistreated by his boss. He shows no remorse for his boss' death.
- Edward Masterman, Ratchett's Valet, who is an Old man and he too is mistreated by his boss.
- Greta Ohlsson, a Swedish missionary, who was the last person to see Ratchett alive before his death.
- Antonio Foscarelli, Italian Car Salesman, who practically fits the description of the murderer for his physical strength.

- Cyrus Hardman, American Private detective, who was hired by Ratchett. He was on guard for him for 24/7 and swore that he never took his eyes off of him. He claimed that a short man with a feminine voice consistently stalked him, who was seen by Hildegarde.
- Pierre Michel, Wagon-lit conductor, who rushed to Ratchett's cabin when he heard a strange noise, came and he claimed that Ratchett replied in French.

In mere eyes, these characters seem like normal people, who happen to be at the Train during the off-season. But, Poirot is a man with keen observation, where even the tiniest detail cannot be missed from his scorching eyes. During the investigation of the passengers, he notices that everyone claims to see someone in the late midnight and must have escaped when the train stopped at the station in between. The story was perfectly aligned with witness and had no room for any mistakes. This perfection bothered Poirot. And he shifts his attention to the Armstrong family. He later found that each of the passengers happens to have a connection with the Armstrong family.

Firstly, Colonel Arbuthnot, who snapped at Poirot, when he accused Mary Debenham. He confessed that it was his doing and Mary had nothing to do about it. Then, it was revealed that he was good friend to Colonel Armstrong. Princess Dragomiroff is actually the Godmother of Mrs. Armstrong and also a good friend to Linda Arden, Grandmother of Daisy. Hildegade Schmidt, former Armstrong family cook, who assisted in the plot and helped to stage the scene. Count Andrenyi was actually forging his wife's passport, he erased the letter 'H' from her passport. His wife's actual name is Helena Goldberg, who is the younger sister to Mrs. Armstrong. He confessed that he took part in the killing instead of his wife. Mary Debenham is the former Armstrong family governess who was deeply devoted to Daisy.

Hector MacQueen, who is the son of the Armstrong family's district attorney, who helped with planning, to avenge for his father's behalf. Edward Masterman is the former Armstrong family batman, who had an immense to Colonel Armstrong. Greta Ohlsson, who is the former family nurse, she used to take care for Daisy. Antonio Foscarelli, former Armstrong family chauffeur who was very close to Colonel. Cyrus Hardman, he secretly loved Armstrong family's maid, who committed Suicide due to the wrong accusation. Pierre Michel, who is the father of the accused maid.

Though everyone had their own reason to kill, they couldn't be able to kill without the mastermind's help in constructing a plan without defects. That Mastermind is turned to be Mrs. Hubbard, who is the grandmother of Daisy and mother of Mrs. Armstrong. Finally, it is revealed that everyone stabbed Ratchett/Cassetti, except Countess. Poirot confronted with everyone and he made a decision of not ratting them out.

Even the passengers killed someone, deep down they are not killers. They get tired of waiting for serving justice to them. So, they took matters to their own hand. Christie justifies the fact that Law never abides with morality always. For which, Christie ended the novel with Poirot saying,

“ ‘In my opinion, M. Poirot,’ he said, ‘the first theory you put forward was the correct one – decidedly so. I suggest that that is the solution we offer to the Yugoslavian police when they arrive. ‘Then’, said Poirot, ‘having placed my solution before you, I have the honour to retire from the case...’ ” (*Murder on the Orient Express*, 274)

In *Murder on the Orient Express*, Hercule Poirot outshines from detective to an Arbiter of Morality, who weighs truth against justice. Poirot's judgment in this case reveals an inevitable question that ‘when the law fails, who decides what is just?’, hence, Christie through Poirot express that the responsibility of justice not lies in law, but in conscience,

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